

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GRAMMAR-TRANSLATION METHOD IN
TEACHING AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7482098>

M.Sh.Miryoqubova

Student National University of Uzbekistan

Annotation: *This paper shows the Effectiveness of Grammar-Translation method in Teaching and Learning of English language. This method of teaching is used to learn the foreign languages. In Uzbekistan “English” as a foreign language for people. In some of educational institutes English is taught a compulsory subject. It is being taught through different methods. Grammar-Translation Method (GTM) is the oldest method of learning any languages. In this paper effectiveness of GTM is proved through quantitative research, analysis and comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of the method.*

Key words: *Grammar-Translation method, effectiveness, teaching English, grammar, literature, grammatical rules, method.*

Every language in the world has its own rules and usage structures and various methods of language learning and teaching help in this. One of the most used methods in the world is the method of grammatical translation. The grammar translation method is a method of teaching foreign languages derived from the classical (sometimes called traditional) method of teaching Greek and Latin. In grammar-translation classes, students learn grammatical rules and then apply those rules by translating sentences between the target language and the native language. Advanced students may be required to translate whole texts word-for-word. The method has two main goals: to enable students to read and translate literature written in the target language, and to further students’ general intellectual development. The grammar–translation method originated from the practice of

teaching Latin. In the early 16th century, Latin was the most widely studied foreign language because of its prominence in government, academia and business. However, the use of Latin then dwindled and was gradually replaced by English, French and Italian. After the decline of Latin, the purpose of learning it in schools changed. Previously, students had learned Latin for the purpose of communication, but it came to be learned as a purely academic subject. Throughout Europe in the 18th and the 19th centuries, the education system was formed primarily around a concept called faculty psychology. The theory dictated that the body and mind were separate and the mind consisted of three parts: the will, emotion and intellect. It was believed that the intellect could eventually be sharpened enough to control the will and emotions by learning Greek and Roman classical literature and mathematics. [Hatfield, Gary (1997). Easton, Patricia (ed.). *Logic and the Workings of the Mind: The Logic of Ideas and Faculty Psychology in Early Modern Philosophy*. Ridgeview Publishing Co. pp.21–45]. Additionally, an adult with such an education was considered mentally prepared for the world and its challenges. This method focuses on reading and writing and has developed methods that more or less facilitate learning to read and write only. As a result, speaking and listening are overlooked.

Grammar and translation classes are usually conducted in the students' native language. Grammar rules are learned deductively; students memorize grammar rules by rote [Richards, Jack C.; Rogers, Theodore S. 2014-04-16], and then practice them by performing grammar exercises and translating sentences into and from the language being studied. More attention is paid to the form of translated sentences than to their content. When students reach a higher level of academic achievement, they can translate entire texts from the language being studied. Tests often consist of translations of classical texts. Listening or speaking is not usually practiced, and very little attention is paid to pronunciation or any communicative aspects of the language. The skill being practiced - this is reading, and then only in the context of translation.

There are a number of reasons why there occur different concepts about “grammar” when one comes across this term. While it is perceived as a part of Linguistics in the course of mother tongue at the secondary school, in teaching and learning foreign language it is considered to be the grammatical side of the speech. According to various scientific sources the word “grammar” could be limited in two notions; 1) the grammatical side of the speech – structural organization of ideas in speaking, listening, reading and writing (e.g., using articles; speech patterns; verb forms of the person adequately to the context) and 2) grammar phenomenon and abstractions (e.g., the first place of the subject in the sentence; the plural form of the noun) [Jalolov J.J, Makhkamova G.T, Ashurov Sh. S, 2015]

The grammar-translation method also has its advantages. As an example, we will take the teaching of English to Russian-speaking people. Many of them can be described with the words "simple study". At the same time, efficiency in certain areas does not suffer, but, on the contrary, increases. So, these are the advantages:

- Suitable for learning a language from scratch. A common problem of many parents who have sent their child to a language center is that children do not understand anything. However, this often applies to adult students who came to study without having the slightest knowledge. Most of these educational institutions speak only English. And it's one thing to say hello and wave, another thing is not to switch to Russian at all. Not all actions can be shown with gestures.

- Saving time. If by some miracle the student still remembers most of what was said, it will happen only after long explanations of certain words (the same gestures, movements, etc.). When all classes last like this, you won't be able to get far. This is especially true for those who urgently need to learn English.

- A person can easily get acquainted with the texts in the original language. Anyone who has dreamed of reading and understanding English classics and other literature can pick up an English-Russian dictionary and look at unfamiliar words there.

- It is more likely that the student will learn the rules. Even in the native language, it is not always possible to understand how Present Perfect differs from Past Simple, especially at the initial stage of training. And there is nothing to say about a foreign language.

Like any other method, the grammar-translation method has disadvantages. They are as follows:

- Lack of communication. Of course, you can use words and grammatical constructions when composing dialogues. Then these dialogues are memorized, most often by heart. That's just in real life there will be no such cliches. In other words, theory is learned in the classroom. And theory is useless without practice.

- Poor speaking skills. Often people learn a language in order to be able to speak with foreigners. But when they meet, they get lost, because, again, they did not practice in the lessons. By the way, residents of foreign countries note that many Russians know grammar perfectly, but they cannot speak well.

- Too much attention is paid to translation. To grasp the essence of what you read, it is not necessary to understand every word. But those who study using the grammar-translation method look into the dictionary every second, which only distracts them from reading.

And giving all these examples, based on historical facts and analyzing the pros and cons of the method of grammatical translation, we can conclude based on the above that the method is relevant in many educational institutions to this day. Thanks to the effectiveness of the translation method into and from the target language, memorizing a number of grammatical rules, structures and words, such skills as reading, writing and grammatical erudition take advantage and increase significantly. With proper study and teaching, this method allows the student or user to read literature in the original language and use the original version of the material, which guarantees the effectiveness of the method and increases the student's abilities.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Agzamova D.B. English Teaching Methodology. (Ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasi) Manual (O'quv qo'llanma) – T.: "Barkamol fayz mediya", 2016, Tashkent, pp 39
2. Bahlsen, Leopold (1905).The Teaching of Modern Languages. Boston: Ginn& Co. pp.12.
3. Chastain, Kenneth.The Development of Modern Language Skills: Theory to Practice. Philadelphia: Center for Curriculum Development,1971.
4. Hatfield, Gary (1997). Easton, Patricia (ed.).Logic and the Workings of the Mind: The Logic of Ideas and Faculty Psychology in Early Modern Philosophy. Ridgeview Publishing Co. pp.21–45.
5. Jalolov J.J, Makhkamova G.T, Ashurov Sh.S, English Language teaching methodology (theory and practice).- T.:”Fan va texnologiya” 2015, Tashkent, pp. 128
6. Richards, Jack C.; Rodgers, Theodore S. (2014-04-16). Approaches and methods in language teaching(Thirded.). New York.
7. Richards &Jack C.; Rodgers, Theodore S. (2001). Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching(2nded.). Cambridge, New York: Cambridge University Press.2001, p.4.
8. Richards, Jack C.; Rodgers, Theodore S. (2001). Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching(2nded.). Cambridge, New York: Cambridge University Press.